

The Impact of Customer Reviews, Hotel Location, and Hotel Price Towards Potential Guests' Intent to Stay at the Ritz-Carlton, Bali

Annarica Tisna^{1*}, Finny Chianata², Joselyn Chandrigo³, Michelle Christy⁴, Valerie⁵

Universitas Pelita Harapan

Corresponding Author: Annarica Tisna annarica@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of customer reviews, hotel location, and hotel price on the intent of potential guests to stay at The Ritz-Carlton, Bali. Through a mixed-methods approach involving surveys, online reviews, and interviews, the research reveals that positive customer reviews significantly contribute to the likelihood of intent to stay, emphasizing the role of online word-of-mouth. Additionally, favorable hotel location emerges as a key driver for guest intent, while the relationship between hotel price and intent proves more complex, indicating a willingness to pay premium prices for positive reviews and desirable locations. These findings provide insights for strategic decision-making in hospitality marketing and management

INTRODUCTION

The development of business competition in Indonesia is a very interesting phenomenon to observe. The impact of globalization has caused the service industry, which consists of various industries such as the telecommunications, transportation, banking and hospitality industries, to develop rapidly (Zeithaml & Bit, 2003).

The hospitality industry is a service industry that offers products and services. Building design, interior and exterior of hotel rooms and restaurants, the atmosphere created in hotel rooms, restaurants and food and beverages sold along with all existing. While the services sold are the hospitality and skills of hotel staff/employees in serving their customers. Services are activities or benefits offered by another party that are essentially intangible and do not result in any ownership. The definition of a service is an activity that has some elements of intangibility that involves some interaction with consumers or property in their possession, and does not result in a transfer of ownership. (Kotler and Armstrong, 2004).

According to Hendriyani, I. G. A. D. (2018), the hospitality industry is a very developing industry in the world, especially in Indonesia itself. This is supported by the statement of the Minister of Tourism, Sandiaga Sallahudin Uno, said that the number of foreign tourists is targeted to reach 7.4 million and the movement of domestic tourists is 1.4 billion. The target value of tourism foreign exchange in 2018 is US\$2.07 billion at the lower limit and US\$5.95 billion at the upper limit. The value of tourism's GDP contribution is 4.1 percent, and exports of creative economy products are estimated to reach US\$26.46 billion or IDR

397.98 trillion. For the added value of the creative economy, it is targeted to reach IDR 1,297 trillion.

Data from the Indonesian Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, foreign tourists who entered Indonesia in April 2019 amounted to 865,810 or 81.22% of the total visits. This number experienced a growth of 276.31% compared to April 2019 which amounted to 230,076 visits.

Figure 1. Number of Visitors in Indonesia by April 2018
 (Source: Badan Pusat Statistik Indonesia, 2018)

The development of the number of hotels in Bali is very rapid, causing competition for hotels in Bali to be very tight. Many things can affect the success of the hospitality business, one of which is how the hotel can attract customers and retain them by providing the best service quality so that guests are satisfied with the services provided. In today's business competition, service is the most important thing for companies to differentiate strategy when they sell the same product. The superior quality of service is expected to be able to attract guests to tend to re-purchase the products we offer.

In addition to good service quality, location and price also play a role in attracting potential guests. People nowadays are critical and very careful in spending money. They consider many factors to choose a product or service, including hospitality services. Therefore, location and price are included in the guest considerations.

The majority of hotel visitors in Bali are foreigners who are having business around the hotel either for tourism, business, or just as a temporary transit place to then continue their trip. Therefore, the strategic location of the hotel is crucial and will make it easier for consumers to gain access to the hotel. The hotel's proximity to several tourist destinations or public facilities will be an additional value for the company. According to Heizer (2001) location has the power to succeed or destroy a company's strategy. Therefore, service providers must seriously consider and select locations that are responsive to possible future economic, demographic, cultural, competitive, and regulatory changes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sann et al. (2019) mentioned that in today's travel landscape, there is a growing trend of travelers making their holiday accommodation bookings online. This shift towards online booking has coincided with an increase in the influence and effectiveness of online peer reviews. Customers perceive peer reviews as more unbiased and reliable, and therefore, they rely on them more than information provided by businesses themselves. Online reviews, notifications, opinions, and recommendations have become crucial in this context.

Furthermore, Kaya et al. (2018) thinks that when travelers make decisions about where to stay at a hotel, they consider specific factors such as the hotel's location and type. In touristy areas, there may be multiple hotels that meet their desired criteria but finding them can be a challenge. When a customer is looking for a hotel to stay at, the first thing he does is ask for the price of the hotel room. The results of research by Fetra et al. (2018) state that price has a positive and significant effect on the decision to stay / stay again at a hotel.

Research Model

Figure 2. Research Model Source: Writer (2018)

METHODOLOGY

This thesis will be opting for a survey technique by handing out questionnaires as a form of quantitative data collection. The questionnaire will include a variety of questions related to their demographic data and variables being researched. It will also be distributed through various social media platforms to increase the reach of and number of participants. In this research, three independent variables which consists of customer reviews (X1), hotel location (X2), and hotel price (X3) will be studied in relation to the dependent variant of guests' intent to stay at The RitzCarlton, Bali.

RESULT

Table 1. Descriptive Statistic Result
Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CustomerReview1	86	3	2	5	4.37	.704
CustomerReview2	86	4	1	5	4.34	.835
CustomerReview3	86	4	1	5	4.51	.763
CustomerReview4	86	4	1	5	4.19	.805
HotelLocation1	86	3	2	5	4.29	.734
HotelLocation2	86	3	2	5	4.34	.806
HotelLocation3	86	2	3	5	4.51	.628
HotelLocation4	86	2	3	5	4.40	.656
HotelPrice1	86	4	1	5	4.00	.854
HotelPrice2	86	4	1	5	3.78	.913
HotelPrice3	86	3	2	5	3.79	.935
IntentToStay1	86	4	1	5	3.65	.891
IntentToStay2	86	4	1	5	2.85	1.023
IntentToStay3	86	4	1	5	3.35	.891
IntentToStay4	86	4	1	5	3.73	1.056
Valid N (listwise)	86					

Statistics

		Customer Review1	Customer Review2	Customer Review3	Customer Review4
N	Valid	86	86	86	86
	Missing	38	38	38	38
Mean		4.37	4.34	4.51	4.19
Median		4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00
Mode		4	5	5	4
Percentiles	25	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
	50	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00
		Hotel Location1	Hotel Location2	Hotel Location3	Hotel Location4
N	Valid	86	86	86	86
	Missing	38	38	38	38
Mean		4.29	4.34	4.51	4.40
Median		4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00
Mode		5	5	5	5

Percentiles	25	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	
	50	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	
	75	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	
		Hotel Price1	Hotel Price2	Hotel Price3	Intent ToStay1	Intent ToStay2
N	Valid	86	86	86	86	86
	Missing	38	38	38	38	38
Mean		4.00	3.78	3.79	3.65	2.85
Median		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	3.00
Mode		4	3	3	4	3
Percentiles	25	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00
	50	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	3.00
	75	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	3.00
		IntentToStay3	IntentToStay4			
N	Valid	86	86			
	Missing	38	38			
Mean		3.35	3.73			
Median		3.00	4.00			
Mode		3	4			
Percentiles	25	3.00	3.00			
	50	3.00	4.00			
	75	4.00	5.00			

Table 2. Frequency Table Customer Review 1
CustomerReview1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	3	2.4	3.5	3.5
	Neutral (Netral)	2	1.6	2.3	5.8
	Agree (Setuju)	41	33.1	47.7	53.5
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	40	32.3	46.5	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 3. Frequency Table Customer Review 2
CustomerReview2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	3.5
	Neutral (Netral)	8	6.5	9.3	12.8
	Agree (Setuju)	31	25.0	36.0	48.8
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	44	35.5	51.2	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 4. Frequency Table Customer Review 3
CustomerReview3

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	3.5
	Neutral (Netral)	2	1.6	2.3	5.8
	Agree (Setuju)	28	22.6	32.6	38.4
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	53	42.7	61.6	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 5. Frequency Table Customer Review 4
CustomerReview4

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	2.3
	Neutral (Netral)	12	9.7	14.0	16.3
	Agree (Setuju)	39	31.5	45.3	61.6
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	33	26.6	38.4	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 6. Hotel Location 1
HotelLocation1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Neutral (Netral)	11	8.9	12.8	14.0
	Agree (Setuju)	36	29.0	41.9	55.8
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	38	30.6	44.2	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 7. Hotel Location 2
HotelLocation2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	2.3
	Neutral (Netral)	12	9.7	14.0	16.3
	Agree (Setuju)	27	21.8	31.4	47.7
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	45	36.3	52.3	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 8. Hotel Location 3
HotelLocation3

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral (Netral)	6	4.8	7.0	7.0
	Agree (Setuju)	30	24.2	34.9	41.9
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	50	40.3	58.1	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 9. Hotel Location 4
HotelLocation4

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral (Netral)	8	6.5	9.3	9.3
	Agree (Setuju)	36	29.0	41.9	51.2
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	42	33.9	48.8	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 10. Hotel Price 1
HotelPrice1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Neutral (Netral)	25	20.2	29.1	30.2
	Agree (Setuju)	32	25.8	37.2	67.4
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	28	22.6	32.6	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 11. Hotel Price 2
HotelPrice2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	1	.8	1.2	1.2
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	3	2.4	3.5	4.7
	Neutral (Netral)	32	25.8	37.2	41.9
	Agree (Setuju)	28	22.6	32.6	74.4
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	22	17.7	25.6	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		

Table 12. Hotel Price 3
IntentToStay1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	2.3
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	7	5.6	8.1	10.5
	Neutral (Netral)	21	16.9	24.4	34.9
	Agree (Setuju)	45	36.3	52.3	87.2
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	11	8.9	12.8	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 13. Intent to Stay 1
IntentToStay1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	2.3
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	7	5.6	8.1	10.5
	Neutral (Netral)	21	16.9	24.4	34.9
	Agree (Setuju)	45	36.3	52.3	87.2
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	11	8.9	12.8	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 14. Intent to Stay 2
IntentToStay2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	5	4.0	5.8	5.8
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	30	24.2	34.9	40.7
	Neutral (Netral)	31	25.0	36.0	76.7
	Agree (Setuju)	13	10.5	15.1	91.9
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	7	5.6	8.1	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 15. Intent to Stay 3
IntentToStay3

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	2	1.6	2.3	2.3
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	10	8.1	11.6	14.0
	Neutral (Netral)	38	30.6	44.2	58.1
	Agree (Setuju)	28	22.6	32.6	90.7
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	8	6.5	9.3	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

Table 16. Intent to Stay 4
IntentToStay4

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree (Sangat tidak setuju)	4	3.2	4.7	4.7
	Disagree (Tidak setuju)	5	4.0	5.8	10.5
	Neutral (Netral)	23	18.5	26.7	37.2
	Agree (Setuju)	32	25.8	37.2	74.4
	Strongly agree (Sangat setuju)	22	17.7	25.6	100.0
	Total	86	69.4	100.0	
Missing	System	38	30.6		
Total		124	100.0		

DISCUSSION

Instrumental Test Result

Table 17. Reliability Statistic
Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	30	85.7
	Excluded ^a	5	14.3
	Total	35	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.796	.813	15

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
CustomerReview1	4.40	.724	30
CustomerReview2	4.20	1.031	30
CustomerReview3	4.77	.430	30
CustomerReview4	3.93	.828	30
HotelLocation1	3.90	.759	30
HotelLocation2	4.07	.868	30
HotelLocation3	4.43	.728	30
HotelLocation4	4.33	.802	30
HotelPrice1	4.13	.860	30
HotelPrice2	3.77	1.006	30
HotelPrice3	3.60	1.037	30
IntentToStay1	3.20	.997	30
IntentToStay2	2.67	1.028	30
IntentToStay3	3.13	1.074	30
IntentToStay4	3.20	1.215	30

	CustomerReview1	CustomerReview2	CustomerReview3	CustomerReview4	HotelLocation1	HotelLocation2	HotelLocation3	HotelLocation4	HotelPrice1	HotelPrice2	HotelPrice3	IntentToStay1	IntentToStay2	IntentToStay3	IntentToStay4
CustomerReview1	1.000	.397	.421	.391	.389	.724	.445	.178	.299	-.057	-.191	-.019	.000	-.027	.259
CustomerReview2	.397	1.000	.342	.582	.379	.331	.662	.626	.202	.346	.303	.094	-.163	.037	.050
CustomerReview3	.421	.342	1.000	.245	.243	.412	.554	.433	.180	.109	.093	.032	-.026	-.080	-.040
CustomerReview4	.391	.582	.245	1.000	.373	.486	.565	.858	.594	.436	.209	.017	-.027	.088	.048
HotelLocation1	.389	.379	.243	.373	1.000	.377	.206	.340	.232	.239	.166	-.064	-.133	.017	.247
HotelLocation2	.724	.331	.412	.486	.377	1.000	.498	.264	.495	.097	.222	.024	.103	-.047	.248
HotelLocation3	.445	.662	.554	.565	.206	.498	1.000	.689	.180	.143	.374	-.029	-.031	-.165	.133
HotelLocation4	.178	.626	.433	.858	.340	.264	.689	1.000	.233	.313	.249	-.086	.014	-.093	-.035
HotelPrice1	.299	.202	.180	.594	.232	.495	.180	.233	1.000	.515	.062	.249	.208	.316	.139
HotelPrice2	-.057	.346	.109	.436	.239	.097	.143	.313	.515	1.000	.106	.186	.122	.317	.293
HotelPrice3	-.191	.303	.093	.209	.166	.222	.374	.249	.062	.106	1.000	.147	-.226	.080	.093
IntentToStay1	-.019	.094	.032	.017	-.064	.024	-.029	-.086	.249	.186	.147	1.000	.303	.876	.336
IntentToStay2	.000	-.163	-.026	-.027	-.133	.103	-.031	.014	.208	.122	-.226	.303	1.000	.323	.580
IntentToStay3	-.027	.037	-.080	.088	.017	-.047	-.165	-.093	.316	.317	.080	.876	.323	1.000	.402
IntentToStay4	.259	.050	-.040	.048	.247	.248	.133	-.035	.139	.293	.093	.336	.580	.402	1.000

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CustomerReview1	53.33	44.092	.402	.817	.785
CustomerReview2	53.53	40.533	.525	.698	.774
CustomerReview3	52.97	46.240	.351	.543	.791
CustomerReview4	53.80	41.269	.614	.749	.769
HotelLocation1	53.83	44.006	.387	.509	.786
HotelLocation2	53.67	41.747	.533	.757	.775
HotelLocation3	53.30	42.907	.529	.809	.777
HotelLocation4	53.40	42.938	.466	.743	.780
HotelPrice1	53.60	41.766	.537	.673	.774
HotelPrice2	53.97	41.620	.450	.659	.780
HotelPrice3	54.13	44.257	.228	.565	.800
IntentToStay1	54.53	43.085	.336	.842	.790
IntentToStay2	55.07	44.961	.178	.671	.804
IntentToStay3	54.60	42.593	.337	.865	.791
IntentToStay4	54.53	40.671	.409	.760	.786

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
57.73	48.478	6.963	15

**Classical Assumption as Result
Normality Test**

Table 18. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		Unstandardized Residual	
N		56	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000	
	Std. Deviation	2.23738495	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.066	
	Positive	.066	
	Negative	-.055	
Test Statistic		.066	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		.200 ^d	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^e	Sig.	.797	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.787
		Upper Bound	.808

a. Test distribution is Normal.
 b. Calculated from data.
 c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
 e. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 2000000.

Asymp. Sig result is 0.2 (> 0.05), shows that it is a normal distribution.

Table 19. Linearity Test
ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Y1 * X1	Between Groups	(Combined)	96.340	8	12.043	1.939	.076
		Linearity	71.549	1	71.549	11.521	.001
		Deviation from Linearity	24.791	7	3.542	.570	.776
Within Groups			291.874	47	6.210		
Total			388.214	55			

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Y1 * X2	Between Groups	(Combined)	117.408	6	19.568	3.541	.005
		Linearity	92.384	1	92.384	16.716	<.001
		Deviation from Linearity	25.024	5	5.005	.906	.485
Within Groups			270.807	49	5.527		
Total			388.214	55			

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Y1 * X3	Between Groups	(Combined)	89.089	7	12.727	2.042	.069
		Linearity	32.957	1	32.957	5.288	.026
		Deviation from Linearity	56.132	6	9.355	1.501	.198
Within Groups			299.126	48	6.232		
Total			388.214	55			

Heteroskedasticity Test

Figure 3. Heteroskedasticity Test

Determination Result Test

Table 21. Determination result test

Model Summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.539 ^a	.291	.250	2.301

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2
 b. Dependent Variable: Y1

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The development of the number of hotels in Bali is very rapid, causing competition for the Ritz-Carlton in Bali to be very tight. Many things can affect the success of the hotel, one of which is how it can attract customers and retain them by providing the best service quality so that guests are satisfied with the services provided. In today's business competition, service is the most important thing for Ritz-Carlton to differentiate strategy when they sell the same product as the competitor. The superior quality of service is expected to be able to attract guests to tend to re-purchase the products we offer. The quality of service is also measured by the price given, the location of the hotel, and the reviews of the previous guest. Those measurements will affect current guests' decision to stay again at another time and impact the next guest candidate to stay at the hotel. Based on the research conducted above, we can align our research model with our four hypotheses from the previous chapter. It is safe to claim that customer reviews will influence potential guests' intent to stay at a certain hotel (H1 accepted). The claim was based on the numbers from the survey. The survey was conducted on 86 validated people, asking them if they are more likely to stay at a hotel with a lot of positive reviews with certain keywords.

Table 22. Surveys Who are More Likely to Stay at Hotels

More likely to stay at a hotel with more reviews.	65.4% (33.1% on Agree and 32.3% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel with a higher average rating.	60.5% (25% on Agree and 35.5% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel with positive reviews.	65.3% (22.6% on Agree and 42.7% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel with reviews that mention specific keywords or phrases that are important to them.	58.1% (31.5% on Agree and 26.6% on Strongly Agree)

Based on the results, more than 50% stated that they are more likely to stay at the hotel with a lot of positive reviews with certain keywords. The survey was also conducted to align with hypothesis 2, hypothesis 3, and hypothesis 4. So, with the result below, we can decide whether our hypotheses are acceptable or unacceptable.

Table 23. Acceptable and Unacceptable Survey Results

More likely to stay at a hotel that is close to tourist attractions.	59.6% (29% on Agree and 30.6% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel that is close to public transportation.	58.1% (21.8% on Agree and 36.3% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel in a safe neighborhood.	64.5% (24.2% on Agree and 40.3% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel with amenities that are important to me.	62.9% (29% on Agree and 33.9% on Strongly Agree)

Based on the results, more than 50% stated that they are more likely to stay at hotels that are close to tourist traps, close to public transportation, and established in a secure environment. Those measurements of the hotel location will affect current guests' decision to stay again at another time and attract the next guest candidate to book a stay at the hotel (H2 accepted).

Table 24. Survey Result

More likely to stay at a hotel with a lower average nightly rate.	48.4% (25.8% on Agree and 22.6% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel with a lower price per star rating.	40.3% (22.6% on Agree and 17.7% on Strongly Agree)
More likely to stay at a hotel during the offseason when prices are lower.	37.1% (16.1% on Agree and 21.0% on Strongly Agree)

Based on the results, less than 50% stated that they are more likely to stay at hotels that offer lower prices on average nightly rate, lower price per star rating, and lower price when it's not peak season. The price set by the hotel influenced potential guest's intention to stay (H3 accepted).

Table 25. Survey Result

Very likely to stay at the Ritz-Carlton, Bali.	45.2% (36.3% on Agree and 8.9% on Strongly Agree)
Willing to pay IDR 7.500.000 or more for a stay at the Ritz-Carlton, Bali.	16.1% (10.5% on Agree and 5.6% on Strongly Agree)
Willing to stay at the Ritz-Carlton, Bali for 529.1% (22.6% on Agree and 6.5% on Strongly Agree)	
Most likely to book a stay at the Ritz-Carlton, Bali through the hotel's website.	43.5% (25.8% on Agree and 17.7% on Strongly Agree)

Based on the results, less than 50% stated that they are more likely to stay at the hotel if Ritz-Carlton even with the price, location, and the review. The attribute offered by the hotel influenced potential guest's intention to stay (H4 accepted).

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to conduct research related to the topic of The Influence of Brand Image, Social Media Advertisement, and Word of Mouth Toward Customer Attraction in order to perfect this research and add insight for readers.

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